

**MODERN AND EFFECTIVE APPROACHES TO TEACHING
ENGLISH IN HIGHER EDUCATION**

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Abstract. One of the advantages of the innovative educational model is the focus on teaching high-level students' personal motivation, non-standard thinking, responsibility, initiative, and the formation of their own attitude to the events around them. Such activities help to develop independence, creativity, productive and critical thinking, and also expand the educational material.

Keywords: English language, method, non-philological direction, technology, teaching, education.

INTRODUCTION

At present, one of the most important issues in education is the purpose, content, methods, tools, organizational forms, imparting knowledge and realizing the educational goal based on the subject material studied in the course of education.

In this paper, we would like to consider the methodological features of teaching English in non-philological universities. That is, turn to the methodology and express your point of view on the methodological foundations of teaching a foreign language for special purposes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Today's modern linguistics includes linguopragmatics, linguoculturology, psycholinguistics, cognitive linguistics, ethnolinguistics, discursive analysis, and the creation of interaction in foreign language teaching and the question of the personality factor in perception is the center of the object of education.

The success and efficiency of foreign language teaching is characterized by the foreign language lesson of the country of study and the uniqueness of its organization,

the age characteristics of the students, the task set before this stage, its content, and the psychological and pedagogical factors related to the beginning of foreign language teaching at this stage. The nature of foreign language teaching in non-philological higher educational institutions largely depends on how teaching is organized and conducted at the initial level of higher education [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Taking into account the experience of teaching English, the following teaching method is proposed. When selecting learning content, divide the lesson into three main parts: a lexical topic, grammatical skills and phonetic exercises.

In the lexical part, the corresponding text in the specialty is selected and the necessary new words and expressions are outlined below. For example, the topic "Types of welding". We get acquainted with the text and the necessary words and expressions such as: Resistance welding, Ultrasonic welding, Gas pressure welding, Explosion pressure welding, Submerge Arc welding.

In the grammatical part of the lesson, in our opinion, it would be correct to study the degrees of comparison of adjectives in English (Degrees of adjectives), because this grammar is close in its property to the text, that is, to the lexical part of the lesson. Students, having become familiar with the types of welding, can use the degrees of comparison of adjectives and make proposals on this topic, which type of welding is more or less effective in the modern world. For example: 1) Ultrasonic welding is more useful for joining dissimilar materials. 2) Resistance spot welding is the most effective for robot automation. In this case, we can provide a link between lexical skills and grammatical skills.

For a phonetic exercise, we will choose a diphthong, for example, [sh] and through listening to various words and expressions for this sound, we develop auditory skills and try to pronounce this sound correctly when reading and speaking. By organizing this type of lesson, firstly, we can integrate all speaking skills, reading, writing and listening skills, as well as enrich the vocabulary of students of non-philological universities with the necessary professional words and terms to correctly

grammatically express their thoughts. Thus, we will be able to meet all the requirements of linguistic competence in the study of linguistic material.

So, E.V. Margaryan believes that the fundamental methodological principles in teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university are the principle of professional communicative orientation and the principle of professional intercultural orientation. The essence of the principle of professional communicative orientation is that training should be based on involving students in oral (speaking, listening) and written (reading, writing) speech, professional communication throughout the entire course of study of the discipline "foreign language", which is an integral part of the general professional training of a specialist. The implementation of this principle ensures the integration of the discipline "Foreign Language" into the general course of professional training of a non-philologist.

Using the experience gained in the course of studying special disciplines, involving students in active creative activity in mastering foreign language speech with a focus on solving communicative professional tasks that involve involuntary memorization of material (problem situations, role-playing games, "round table", etc.), the selection of linguistic material that reflects the linguistic essence of a specialist's professional statements provides real assistance in their future practical activities. As part of the communicative approach to professionally oriented teaching of a foreign language, we also consider it necessary to take into account the methodological principle of learning interactivity, which involves connecting students to such a "model of interpersonal communication, which is aimed at developing cooperation, focused on the interaction of communication participants, striving for social partnership, dialogue to achieve a practical goal.

Of course, professionally-oriented teaching of a foreign language requires the integration of the discipline "Foreign Language" with major disciplines. It also requires that the subject be focused on the latest achievements in a particular area of human activity, timely reflect scientific achievements in areas that directly affect the

professional interests of students, and provide them with an opportunity for professional growth.

Based on this, we would like to propose another method for developing a lesson in a non-philological university in the process of teaching English. This method is called KWL (Know, Want to Know, Learned). The KWL chart was compiled by Donna Ogle. It can be used in all types of teaching and various subjects, in large or small groups. The spreadsheet is a comprehension strategy that helps activate pre-reading knowledge and engage the student in learning.

Table 1.

Method «KWL».

Know	Want to know	Learn
Information about what students know	Information about what students want to learn	After completing the lesson, the information that the students received

This method is very useful when working on a new topic because it is based on the interests, requests and needs of the students. For example, we are introducing a new topic to our students as Welding science and other subjects. First, draw a three-column table on the board and ask the students to write on the first column what they know about the science of welding and how it relates to other subjects.

Students will write everything they know about it, then they will fill in the second column, that is, what they want to know about the science of Welding and how it relates to other sciences. After analyzing all the answers of the students, the teacher distributes the texts, and together they study and explain this material. In the process of reading, students learn new words, answer questions given at the end of the text, and work according to scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Communication and interaction of general specialized disciplines.

At the end of the assignment, students complete the third last column (Learned), what they have learned. From these notes, the teacher can find out how much the current level of students' knowledge on this topic has changed and what their desire is to work according to this method. Students can add any new questions on this topic over time.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I would like to say that our ideas about the methodological aspects of teaching English to students of non-philological universities are based on the views of many researchers. I would like to present specific proposals on the materials of this article:

- 1) select the content of training based on an analysis of the needs of students;
- 2) take into account the connections of special disciplines with the English language;
- 3) create situational exercises necessary for further professional activity;
- 4) develop critical thinking, starting with asking questions and clarifying problems.

It seems that the methods described by us can be useful in organizing the educational process and integrating special disciplines.

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